

LESSONS LEARNED: A TECHNICAL BRIEF

ENHANCING THE ADOPTION AND UTILIZATION OF BIOFORTIFIED LEGUMES – A CASE OF ZIRON PULSE PROJECT IN KENYA

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

FANRPAN and four other institutions (Hutton Institute, University of Nairobi, University of Birmingham, and KALRO Food Crops Research Institute Kenya) submitted a proposal for funding to BBSRC on collaboration research titled “ZIRON Pulse: Upscaling adoption and exploitation of a wide diversity of Iron and Zinc-rich beans by rural populations in Africa”. The research started in July 2020 and has run until February 2023. The main objectives of the research were to obtain new knowledge related to micronutrient-fortified bean innovations and provide essential underpinning science that contributes to global food and nutritional security, economic development and growth through the development of health-promoting common bean varieties with proven nutritional efficacy.

FANRPAN work package focused on coming up with strategies of enhancing adoption and utilization of the ZIRON pulse by developing a tool kit package for mobilization, sensitization, educating commercialization and engagement of various stakeholders and players in the whole bean value chains.

This technical brief (Lessons Learned) presents the lessons learnt in promoting the adoption and utilization of biofortified bean (ZIRON pulse) varieties in Kenya. Against the background of a desk review and formative research carried out prior to promoting the ZIRON pulse, with the aim of identifying and mapping the status of biofortified bean utilization and consumption and barriers associated with, the strategies shared in this brief are key lessons to consider when introducing a new technology/innovation(seed) to the general population.

To achieve the objective of ensuring that the newly introduced bean breed is widely accepted, adopted and utilized by consumers and different actors in the bean value chain, FANRPAN employed a number of ways of engagement. Overall, FANRPAN packaged these approaches under a tool kit, which was a compendium of different information customized and contextualized for various Bean value chain actors.

A formative survey was conducted in Kiambu, Meru and Nyeri Counties of Kenya. This survey sought to find out the challenges and enablers for scaling up and adoption of Ziron beans in the community focusing on mothers/caregivers, traders, agricultural extension workers, and farmers. It also aimed to determine the gaps in knowledge about biofortified beans so that that they can be addressed in the Nutrition toolkit. The main gaps identified included lack of knowledge on the nutritional and health benefits of beans, misconceptions and myths on biofortified crops, lack of innovative methods of making beans apart from the traditional methods, lack of certified seeds and lack of awareness on biofortified beans.

A desk reviews was conducted which led to a stakeholder mapping exercise of the counties to be used for the ZIRON pulse implementation activity. More specifically, the mapping and assessment sought to map all bean players (farmers, traders, mothers/caregivers, general public and agricultural extension workers) in the counties of Kiambu, Nyeri and Meru of Kenya.

After identifying various actors in the bean value chain (consumers, traders, farmers, policy makers, leaders etc), the content for different actors was identified and packaged in different forms of fliers, manuals, comics, cooking demonstrations, and dissemination approaches were also different, ranging from group sessions, to campaigns, to farmer field days to workshops.

A recipe book “*Ziron-Pulse Promoting the Consumption and adoption of Beans using a variety of ways*” was developed and pretested by adopting bean recipes from various sources such as the Kenyan Food Recipes by FAO and Government of Kenya (GoK), local Chefs and households, and the Zambian bean recipe book. It aims at providing a practical guideline to bean preparation at household levels and for traders that sell food for enhanced diet quality and improved nutrition

and health. It is expected to help promote the consumption and adoption of beans among vulnerable population. The book was designed for extension officers, community nutritionists and Community Health Volunteers (CHVs) to help them provide step by step instructions to communities and households on how to prepare and consume common bean using various recipes. The use of various recipes is vital in promoting the upscaling, consumption and adoption of common bean.

Key lessons learned included:

- Research before introducing a new biofortified crop variety in any community
 - awareness raising and demand creation before introducing biofortified crop varieties into the community.
 - Create an enabling environment by taking a multisectoral approach by working with public and private sector partners across the value chain.
 - Need for capacity strengthening of value chain actors.
 - Establishing a monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) system to track and assess delivery progress, utilization of seed, adoption of varieties, and consumption of biofortified foods, as well as gather feedback from farmers and consumers about biofortified crops and foods is important.
- Implication for Policy
- Local trials are needed when introducing new innovations in Agriculture to ensure that it is culturally acceptable and allow farmers and other actors have an in-depth understanding of the product they are dealing with.
 - Cost effective strategies like biofortification to be prioritized to manage micronutrients deficiency.
 - Identify national opportunities for improving micronutrient provision and determine whether biofortified crops can make a valuable contribution, in concert with other interventions.
 - Investment in national agricultural research.
 - Government should facilitate the registration, certification and production of biofortified seeds or cuttings to allow for private and public sector multiplication and distribution so that seed is available for farmers.
 - Government to invest in effective delivery strategies to provide with knowledge on biofortified crops.
 - Awareness creation through active social marketing, gender-sensitive extension guidance and via public sector procurement
 - Support the growing but critical evidence-base on costs and effectiveness of biofortification strategies, and widely share success stories and best practices.

1.0 PROJECT BACKGROUND

FANRPAN and four other institutions (Hutton Institute, University of Nairobi, University of Birmingham, and KALRO Food Crops Research Institute Kenya) submitted a proposal for funding to BBSRC on collaboration research titled “ZIRON Pulse: Upscaling adoption and exploitation of a wide diversity of Iron and Zinc-rich beans by rural populations in Africa”. The research started in July 2020 and has run until February 2023. The main objectives of the research were to obtain new knowledge related to micronutrient-fortified bean innovations and provide essential underpinning science that contributes to global food and nutritional security, economic development and growth through the development of health-promoting common bean varieties with proven nutritional efficacy. The overarching aim of this project was to obtain new knowledge related to micronutrient-fortified bean innovations and provide essential underpinning science that contributes to global food and nutritional security, economic development and growth through the development of health-promoting common bean varieties with proven nutritional efficacy. FANRPAN work package focused on coming up with strategies of enhancing adoption and utilization of the ZIRON pulse by developing a tool kit package for mobilization, sensitization, educating commercialization and engagement of various stakeholders and players in the whole bean value chains.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

This technical brief (Lessons Learned) presents the lessons learnt in promoting the adoption and utilization of biofortified bean (ZIRON pulse) varieties in Kenya. Against the background of a desk review and formative research carried out prior to promoting the ZIRON pulse, with the aim of identifying and mapping the status of biofortified bean utilization and consumption and barriers associated with, the strategies shared in this brief are key lessons to consider when introducing a new technology/innovation(seed) to the general population. Coming up with an agricultural technology/innovation is one thing, ensuring that end users have accepted it and are ready to utilize it is another thing. The process does not happen in a vacuum, strategic engagement of end users is very critical if the newly introduced innovation will be accepted and utilized. Cultural barriers and lack of enough information may hinder some innovations/ technology from being adopted, no matter how accurate scientists maybe with the product.

2.0 METHODS

To achieve the objective of ensuring that the newly introduced bean breed is widely accepted, adopted and utilized by consumers and different actors in the bean value chain, FANRPAN employed a number of ways of engagement. Overall, FANRPAN packaged these approaches under a tool kit, which was a compendium of different information customized and contextualized for various Bean value chain actors. Before this information was compiled, certain processes had to be carried out so that the content was relevant and specific to each group of value chain actors and consumers.

2.1 FORMATIVE RESEARCH

A formative survey was conducted in Kiambu, Meru and Nyeri Counties of Kenya. This survey sought to find out the challenges and enablers for scaling up and adoption of Ziron beans in the community focusing on mothers/caregivers, traders, agricultural extension workers, and farmers. It also aimed to determine the gaps in knowledge about biofortified beans so that that they can be addressed in the Nutrition toolkit.

Findings indicated that plant-based food items were mainly consumed in the three counties with most of the families taking three meals a day; breakfast, lunch, and dinner however, children under five years were frequently fed with at least five meals a day. Yellow beans were the most preferred variety for consumption in the three counties followed by the kidney beans locally known as “wairimu”.

There seemed to be rise of bean consumption in the community in the recent years which was attributed to increase in the cases of chronic diseases like diabetes and cancer. The community believed that consumption of beans helps prevent the occurrence of such diseases and in their management. Additionally, beans had the ability to be easily combined with other foods.

Beans were initiated to children as relish, then green beans before proceeding to dry beans. However, the introduction of beans as relish was not a very common practice as they were viewed as foreign and those that tried consuming complained of it being tougher than other green leafy vegetables. Dry beans were the most popular and were prepared by boiling then mashing and adding potatoes (Mukimo) or taken with ugali and rice. Thus, they were readily available in the markets.

The community had misconceptions that biofortified beans had failure to germinate and hence waste of rainy seasons. Others reported that biofortified foods could cause diseases such as cancer, obesity, and enlargement of hormones. A few respondents associated biofortified foods with GMO and claimed that this information was passed through media like radios. Most mothers reported that GMOs do not cook, and also claimed that they are dried using electricity and thus hard to cook. Additionally, some respondents reported not consuming biofortified foods due to preference. However, a few other respondents reported not having a problem with biofortified foods.

Most of the respondents named various sources of animal proteins including meat, fish, milk, eggs, dairy products, and chicken. Others reported on the plant sources of proteins as cereals and nuts. When asked about the health and nutritional benefits of beans, some respondents stated that beans provide proteins and carbohydrates and are essential in the management of disease like cancer and diabetes.

Overall, there are two seasons of bean production during the year as reported by the respondents, these are the seasons where most farmers plant beans. The two seasons are classified as the long and short rains, the long rains are from March to April and the short rains

are majorly from October to November. Farmers choice of bean varies to grow during these seasons was based on productivity and marketability.

A great number of respondents in Kiambu and Nyeri county reported being aware of government and organization interventions targeting fruits, vegetables, and protein sources of foods.

The farmers reported that the main challenge they experience in beans production is attack by pests and diseases such frost, worms like millipedes, halo blight, rust and aphids and attacks by animals like hare which feeds on the bean leaves. In addition, farmers reported a problem with storage which caused a lot of post-harvest losses because of attacks from pests. Farmers further reported on the change of climate, which has resulted in the unpredictability of rain further reducing the production of beans.

Most the mothers also reported on health-related challenges associated with bean consumption such as bloated stomach, acidity, allergies, and constipation especially when consuming certain bean varieties like “Wairimu”. A few respondents reported on the challenge of cooking, due to lack of fuel for cooking, and some beans take longer to cook. However, the length of time taken to cook was reported to be associated with how the beans were harvested.

The following were recommendations from the study:

- i. Respondents suggested being educated about the information on side effects of biofortified foods
- ii. Respondents should be trained on proper bean cooking methods
- iii. The community members suggested to educated on the issue of avid during storage
- iv. Respondents asked if the traditional varieties do not have zinc and iron compared to the biofortified beans
- v. Respondents, especially farmers suggested being informed on the size of land needed to grow the biofortified foods, as well as the return on investments

2.3 DESK REVIEW

Worldwide, iron and zinc deficiencies are major public health problems and they are often associated with the phenomenon “hidden hunger” [1]. Hidden hunger is a form of malnutrition that occurs when the intake or absorption of micronutrients is too low to maintain a good health and development and is mainly caused by a combination of poor diet, disease, and increased micronutrient needs [2].

Food-based strategies, such as dietary diversification and food fortification, are considered effective approaches to prevent and combat hidden hunger [3]. However, their effectiveness largely depends on necessary changes in behavior and diet and could therefore be more difficult to reach [4].

A relatively new food-based strategy to reduce hidden hunger is biofortification, the breeding process that develops and deploys micronutrient-rich staple crops aiming to improve the nutritional statuses of resource-poor populations [5, 6]. Biofortification is a nutrition-sensitive agricultural intervention that is relatively inexpensive, cost-effective, and sustainable considering it involves a single investment in breeding ultimately leading to nutritionally improved crops that will continue to be grown and consumed year after year. By aiming at staple foods, which are predominately present in the diets of poor people, the target population is already familiarized with the crop of interest and this ought to facilitate adoption. Furthermore, biofortification may be widely accessible, also for people living in remote areas and with limited resources.

Beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) can be considered important staple crops in Kenya. The common bean is widely affordable, contains substantial amounts of protein, fibers and classifies as a source of iron and zinc. Although the concentration of iron in beans is high, bioavailability is influenced by many dietary factors such as food processing techniques, meal composition, the presence of organic acids and antinutrients including polyphenols and phytates [5]. Previously, it was thought that polyphenols are the main inhibitors of successful iron absorption from beans [7]. However, Petry et al. [8] demonstrated that phytic acid is the major inhibitor of iron absorption in beans and that the influence of polyphenols is low when beans are eaten as part of a composite diet.

Biofortification might cause changes in physical and sensory properties of beans, and this could possibly interfere with the consumer acceptability of the newly bred varieties [6]. Without acceptance, biofortified beans most likely will not be consumed, obliterating their potential to improve nutritional statuses of vulnerable populations [9].

2.4 STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

The overall purpose was to undertake a stakeholder mapping exercise at national and county levels. More specifically, the mapping and assessment sought to map all bean players (farmers, traders, mothers/caregivers, general public and agricultural extension workers) in the counties of Kiambu, Nyeri and Meru of Kenya (Figure 1).

Nyeri county is in the Central region of Kenya and majorly inhabited by the Kikuyu ethnic group. Agriculture is the main economic backbone of the county and one of its key county objectives is, improving production in agriculture and general food and nutrition security. The main food crops planted in the county are maize, beans, peas, potatoes, and vegetables. Livestock farming such as dairy cattle, goats, and chicken is also widely practiced in the county.

Meru county is the leading county in horticulture production in Kenya. Agriculture is the major economic activity in this county due to the rich volcanic soils in the high-altitude areas. Coffee, tea, French-beans and dairy products as primary produce. Wholesale and retail trade also play important role in the county's economy.

Kiambu County is located within Nairobi Metropolitan Region. Its capital is Kiambu, and its largest town is Thika. The county has a population of 2, 417, 735 with 40% rural and 60% urban. Kikuyu is the main dominant tribe in the county. Agriculture is the leading economic activity in Kiambu county as the soil fertility is conducive for livestock keeping and production of various crops. Agriculture contributes to about 17% of the population's income. Its proximity to Nairobi, the capital city of Kenya, also makes it a potential fresh food basket for the urbanities. Climate change, increase in population, and consequently, a reduction in agricultural land areas per family has reduced decline agricultural production.

Figure 1: Showing counties of Kenya

2.5 THE TOOL KIT – A COMPENDIUM OF THE NUTRITION TOOLKIT ACTIVITIES

After identifying various actors in the bean value chain (consumers, traders, farmers, policy makers, leaders etc), the content for different actors was identified and packaged in different forms of fliers, manuals, comics, and dissemination approaches were also different, ranging from group sessions, to campaigns, to workshops.

2.5.1 NUTRITION RESOURCE MANUAL-FOR EXTENSION WORKERS

This resource manual on bean utilization and consumption aimed to provide nutrition information to the farmers participating in ZIRON trials but specifically information on Zinc and Iron rich bean nutrition. The manual was custom developed for extension workers and other practitioners who promote good nutrition. The knowledge gained from this resource manual will enhance understanding of biofortification and influence the choice of the seed and beans for food (Appendix I & Appendix II).

2.5.2 FLIERS - FOR CONSUMERS AND GENERAL PUBLIC, TRADERS, FARMERS, FOOD VENDORS, MOTHERS AND CAREGIVERS

A total of 4 fliers were developed and each of them contained the following information:

Flier information for mothers and caregivers (Appendix III)

- i. Good Nutrition
- ii. Importance of legumes (beans) for growth
- iii. Different ways of processing and utilizing beans
- iv. Feeding under five children- beans in infant meals
- v. Nutrition for pregnant and lactating mothers- beans
- vi. Meal planning – including beans in the diet
- vii. Hygiene and Safety during meal preparation

Flier information for consumers/general public (Appendix III)

- i. Good nutrition
- ii. Importance of beans in nutrition
- iii. Different ways of utilizing beans in meals
- iv. Bean processing

Flier information for retailers, traders (Appendix III)

- i. Good nutrition
- ii. Importance of beans in nutrition
- iii. Food safety in bean marketing

Flier for farmers (Appendix III)

- i. Good Nutrition
- ii. Importance of legumes (beans) in the diet
- iii. Different ways of processing and utilizing beans

2.5.3 BEAN RECIPE BOOK

A recipe book *“Ziron-Pulse Promoting the Consumption and adoption of Beans using a variety of ways”* was developed by adopting bean recipes from various sources such as the Kenyan Food Recipes by FAO and Government of Kenya (GoK), local Chefs and households, and the Zambian bean recipe book. It aims at providing a practical guideline to bean preparation at household levels and for traders that sell food for enhanced diet quality and improved nutrition and health. It is expected to help promote the consumption and adoption of beans among vulnerable population especially pregnant and lactating women and young children below the age of five years in Kenya. This is because, despite common bean's high nutritive value in terms of energy, protein and micronutrient content, young children often do not get the full nutrition benefit from beans because they are unable to utilize the beans in the most common prepared form for consumption in households. Monotonous preparation of beans also limits consumption by pregnant women who are sensitive to food sensory characteristics such as smell and taste.

This recipe book also seeks to serve as a nutrition education tool in providing guidance in the provision of healthy diets to households and individuals. These recipes will contribute in improving nutrition status of the target population. This beans recipe book should be promoted hand in hand with nutrition and health education and the bean nutrition resource kit.

The book was designed for extension officers, community nutritionists and Community Health Volunteers (CHVs) to help them provide step by step instructions to communities and

households on how to prepare and consume common bean using various recipes. The use of various recipes is vital in promoting the upscaling, consumption and adoption of common bean. The book therefore provides recipes for preparing bean purees of various types, bean flour for preparing porridges and other products. The purees and porridge are good for children and other population groups that are not able to eat solid food. The recipes are presented in the following order; Bean purees, Bean flour and porridge, Bean snacks, Bean dishes and Bean soups (Appendix III & V).

2.5.4 COMIC BOOK FOR SCHOOL CHILDREN

Ensuring that children are positioned as agents of change, as they are strategic information disseminators, the comic book teaches them how good nutrition can be achieved through access to nutrient dense food like biofortified beans which can address specific nutritional disorders among family members. Children as the next generation of researchers, food scientists, nutritionists and actors in the bean value chains, their involvement in and understanding of biofortification is very important (Appendix III).

2.5.5 SEED MULTIPLICATION

We supported the University of Nairobi to set up demonstration plots in Kiambu and Nyeri counties using farmer demonstration farms to teach farmers on best practices of bean production (Appendix IV). However, due to rainfall failure, we did not harvest much from the plots so we sourced beans from KALRO for cooking demonstrations.

2.5.6 COOKING DEMONSTRATIONS

Cooking demonstrations to promote the use of various bean recipes were carried out in Kiambu County where more than 30 recipes were tried in the community to promote the consumption and adoption of ZIRON pulse (Appendix III).

At the end of the cooking demonstrations, the participants tasted all the foods after which they evaluated them on a scale of 1-5 using a questionnaire. A rating of 5 meant that it is the most preferred and 1 being the least preferred. The questionnaire assessed different aspects of the bean recipes and whether they could address the identified gaps in nutrition.

Generally, participants rated the recipes highly with most of them scoring 4 and above and with only 1 scoring a 3. This means that they liked and enjoyed the recipes. All the recipes tried did not cause flatulence meaning that they can be easily adopted by the community.

2.5.7 COMMERCIALIZATION AND AWARENESS OF ZIRON PULSE

This was done through farmer field days, Radio spots in local FM stations, TV coverage, print media in the leading dailies and social media to create awareness of ZIRON pulse in the community. The exercise was a great success because we participated in 4 farmer field days (Approximately 400 participants) and we disseminated health and nutrition messages on FANRPAN and Ziron Pulse to the framers and the general population. We got coverage in the local FM stations (Inooro and Radio Maisha) which covered kikuyu and Kiswahili audiences. We did coverage on the national TV stations like KTN, Ebru and NTV. We also created awareness on Twitter and Facebook social media platforms (Appendix V).

2.5.8 EVALUATION OF THE NUTRITION PERFORMANCE OF THE NUTRITION TOOLKIT

The Nutrition toolkit was developed to address these nutrition and health information gaps that had been identified from a formative research that was done in Kiambu, Nyeri and Meru counties of Kenya.

The evaluation was conducted using Focus group discussions (FGD) and in-depth interviews to collect information related to knowledge, attitude, and practices on biofortified beans, and bean processing methods adopted by the communities, sources of information on biofortified beans, availability of biofortified beans, recipes tried at home, barriers to biofortified bean consumption and what consumers like most about biofortified beans. This information was gathered in order to evaluate the performance of the nutrition toolkit in terms of addressing gaps identified in formative research.

The study found out that the high cost of the biofortified beans was a major hinderance to their consumption and adoption and hence suggested that the price should be reduction to make them accessible. Additionally, there was lack of information on where to buy the beans. Participants also needed information on different planting techniques that can be used to maximize on the yield of biofortified beans.

Overall, the rural communities were aware of and generally had a positive perception towards consumption, benefits and utilization of biofortified beans. The knowledge of biofortified beans was found to significantly influence their perception and utilization of biofortified beans. There was still low knowledge on the health and nutrition benefits of biofortified beans meaning that more awareness needs to be made. The number of recipes being tried were still low and more cooking demonstrations are needed. There was still lack of knowledge on where to source biofortified beans. Therefore, research institutes and relevant stakeholders should ensure that rural sensitization is promoted at a higher scale with accompanying cooking demonstration, and availing the biofortified beans to improve acceptability and utilization. There is still need for sensitization and education for the members of Nyeri County on the ZIRON-Pulse beans varieties. Consecutively, more seeds should be made available for the farmers to plant and distribute once harvested.

2.6 FANRPAN REGIONAL MULTI-STAKEHOLDER POLICY DIALOGUE: RESILIENT AFRICAN FOOD SYSTEMS - SOLUTIONS FOR CLIMATE CHANGE, LIVELIHOODS, FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY”.

The Policy Dialogue came at the tail-end of FANRPAN’s 2016-2023 strategy, which focused on “building resilient African agriculture and food systems, securing prosperity and health for all”. The dialogue presented an excellent opportunity for the network to reflect on achievements and progress registered so far. It also provided a dynamic platform for stakeholders to come together to take stock of key processes, identify their roles and how they can be linked to accelerate transformation. The Policy Dialogue showcased solutions and elevated pathways to food systems transformation.

FANRPAN’s sub themes of focus in the dialogue were on Accelerating Climate Resilience, Shifting to Sustainable and Healthier diets and Strengthening Institutions and Systems for Resilient Food Systems. The ZIRON pulse research trial is one of the FANRPAN’s projects under Nutrition

Sensitive Agriculture whose research activities aimed to generate evidence on addressing micronutrient deficiencies through nutrient dense -food based interventions(biofortification). The research processes and results fed into the understanding of how to support local communities and food systems make a shift to sustainable and healthier diets while building capacity of national and local institutions for resilient food systems in Kenya. The FANRPAN Regional Multi-stakeholder Policy dialogue offered a platform where ZIRON Pulse research information was widely disseminated beyond Kenya. These lessons and results are relevant and applicable across Africa, especially for countries that are currently finding challenges addressing child and maternal micronutrient deficiencies.

3.0 KEY LESSONS

1. Before introducing a new biofortified crop variety in any community, it is important to establishing, through research, existing fears, cultural beliefs and held misconceptions that can hinder adoption of the new breed
2. There is need for awareness raising and demand creation before introducing biofortified crop varieties into the community. This can be done through
 - (a) messages on the production, nutrition, and health benefits of biofortified crops, (
 - b) promotional materials, and
 - (c) a strategy for dissemination of key messages. This is to ensure that consumers are aware of the crops and hence demand for them.
3. It is crucial to create an enabling environment by taking a multisectoral approach by working with public and private sector partners across the value chain, including researchers, policy-makers, businesses, farmers, and civil society organizations to promote the consumption and adoption biofortified crops.
4. When introducing any biofortified crop to the community, there is need for capacity strengthening of value chain actors. This can be done through developing training materials and providing financial and practical support for value chain actors (eg, Extension workers, seed multipliers, farmers, the general public, mothers/caregivers, traders, and processors).
5. Establishing a monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) system to track and assess delivery progress, utilization of seed, adoption of varieties, and consumption of biofortified foods, as well as gather feedback from farmers and consumers about biofortified crops and foods is important. This will help generate evidence and lessons learned on the adoption and utilization of biofortified crops. Additionally, it will help assess the cost-effectiveness of various delivery models and strategies and provides much-needed feedback to delivery teams to recalibrate delivery strategies.

4.0 IMPLICATION FOR POLICY

1. Any newly introduced innovation in Agriculture, like biofortified seed, has to undergo trials locally to ensure that it is culturally acceptable and allow farmers and other actors have an in-depth understanding of the product they are dealing with.
2. To manage micronutrients deficiency, also known as hidden hunger, it is critical to ensure that approaches like biofortification are prioritized as this is an affordable means of reaching a larger population in a healthier way compared to supplementation.
3. It is critical to identify national opportunities for improving micronutrient provision and determine whether biofortified crops can make a valuable contribution, in concert with other interventions.

4. Investment in national agricultural research is important to generate or adapt crop varieties to have high content of essential vitamins and minerals while, at the same time, providing higher yields that will be attractive to producers. Opportunities for conventional breeding approaches should be identified and governments may wish to consider as well the pros and cons of transgenic approaches;
5. The government should facilitate the registration, certification and production of biofortified seeds or cuttings to allow for private and public sector multiplication and distribution so that seed is available for farmers.
6. The government should invest in effective delivery strategies to provide poor smallholder producers, both women and men, knowledge of, and access to biofortified crops, and promote their adoption and in-home consumption.
7. There is need to promote uptake by farmers and consumption by targeting nutritionally-vulnerable populations through active social marketing, gender-sensitive extension guidance and potentially also via public sector procurement that supports institutional feeding programmes (such as in school feeding).
8. It is important to support the growing but critical evidence-base on costs and effectiveness of biofortification strategies, and widely share success stories and best practices. Biofortification has the potential to reach large numbers of nutritionally vulnerable people, but measuring and tracking is important to understanding whether this potential is being achieved. Therefore, governments should invest in the data gathering and reporting systems to evaluate the effectiveness of all interventions aimed at improving agriculture, health and nutrition.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: NUTRITION RESOURCE KIT PRETESTED MATERIAL

APPENDIX II: NUTRITION TOOLKIT FINAL MATERIALS

<h1>NUTRITION RESOURCE KIT</h1> <p>For Biofortified Beans Consumption and Adoption</p>		<p>Lessons 14</p> <p>Mark 15</p> <p>Site Identity 15</p> <p>Malnutrition: 16</p> <p>Action: discuss and agree with families some of the following Positive steps to take: 20</p> <p>Conclusion of the theme 20</p> <p>Theme 2: Dietary Diversity: Pulses- beans, cowpeas, ground nuts, or nuts nutrients and health benefits 20</p> <p>Fat pulses: beans, cowpeas, ground nuts, or nuts daily to maintain good health. All these foods are rich sources of protein and a good substitute for meat. 23</p> <p>2.1 Getting to know pulses, nuts and seeds 23</p> <p>Theme objectives: 24</p> <p>Key Information for the session 24</p> <p>2.2 Healthy benefits of eating pulses, nuts and seeds 24</p> <p>Theme 3: Biofortified beans 25</p> <p>Theme objectives: 25</p> <p>How to facilitate this session 25</p> <p>Facilitation requirements 25</p> <p>Discussion Questions 25</p> <p>Key Information for the session 25</p> <p>Techniques of Biofortification 26</p> <p>Biofortification Examples 26</p> <p>Benefits of Biofortification 26</p> <p>Theme 4: beans and Family Feeding 27</p> <p>How to facilitate this session 27</p> <p>Facilitation requirements 27</p>
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<p>Discussion Questions 27</p> <p>Key Information for the session 27</p> <p>Nutritional Benefits of Beans for Babies 27</p> <p>How to Prepare Beans for Babies 28</p> <p>Theme 5: Meal planning (how often should beans be consumed?) 28</p> <p>Objectives of the Theme 28</p> <p>How to facilitate this session 29</p> <p>Facilitation requirements 29</p> <p>Discussion Questions 29</p> <p>Key Information for the session 29</p> <p>Why is meal planning important? 29</p> <p>What are the benefits of meal planning? 29</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Meal-planning saves you time 29 2. Save at the checkout 29 3. Plan for a healthier diet 30 4. 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Specifically, we appreciate the leadership, efforts and encouragement rendered to us by Prof. Sibeswabe Sibanda and Sibeswabe Mwanakanda, both of FANRPAN.</p> <p>We further wish to acknowledge the tireless efforts made by the following individuals during the developmental process of this booklet:</p> <p>Bastien Kage – Nutrition Associate- FAIRFARM Betha Marshall – Nutrition Advisor- FAIRFARM Eric Ouyang – Freelance Chef, Nairobi, Kenya</p> <p>About FAIRFARM</p> <p>Ziron-Pulse is project by the Food, Agriculture and Natural Resources Policy Analysis Network (FANRPAN) which is a pan-African network that provides independent evidence to inform policy processes at national and regional levels. FANRPAN's membership includes food, agriculture and natural resources (FANR) related government departments, parliamentarians, research and farmer organizations, private sector, civil society organizations and the media. FANRPAN's multi-stakeholder network's structure consists of a regional secretariat and established national nodes in 17 African countries.</p> <p>As a leading voice for food and nutrition security policies on the continent, FAIRFARM has a reach that goes from local communities to the regional level, has extensive experience in managing and implementing multi-faceted FANR, initiatives, and works with different technical and funding partners across the globe. To deliver on its vision of "resilient African agriculture and food systems, securing prosperity and health for all", FAIRFARM focuses on three strategic goals for (i) creation agriculture and food systems through the development and implementation of evidence-based policies; (ii) ensure adequate, safe and nutritious food; and (iii) promote climate change resilience and resource sustainable food systems. These strategic goals are achieved through two themes, namely Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) and Nutrition. Sustainable Agriculture (NSA), supported by institutional capacity strengthening is delivered on the NSA goal. FAIRFARM seeks to see the adoption of evidence-based policies to improve and ensure access to diverse and nutritious</p>	<p>dense food. In particular, FAIRFARM works to promote policies across the agricultural value chain that promote NSA.</p> <p>FAIRFARM promotes policies that reduce barriers to entry for nutrient-rich livestock, seeds and fresh into markets, and encourage farmers to make nutrient-sensitive choices in the production of livestock and crops through market mechanisms and education. FAIRFARM promotes policies that support storage practices that reduce post-harvest loss and nutrient loss through the uptake of technology and education. Furthermore, FAIRFARM promotes processing technologies such as food fortification and biofortification to improve access to nutritious foods for consumers to improve the overall health of populations. FAIRFARM advocates for policies and initiatives that aim to make farmers and consumers (particularly women who grow up to 80% of the continent's food) more informed about the choices impacting the nutrition of their communities or families, hopefully driving demand for nutrient-rich food.</p> <p>FAIRFARM also promotes greater investment into NSA programs by the private sector and development investors. In delivering on the NSA goal, FAIRFARM is implementing two projects in Kenya (i) Improving Dietary and Health Outcomes for Women-Playing in Agriculture and Nutrition Actors in Africa. The project is being implemented in Kenya and is funded by the International Development Research Centre (IDRC). The project started in September 2018 and is due to end in August 2022. (ii) Ziron Pulse: Upgrading adoption and utilization of a wide diversity of Iron and Zinc-rich beans by rural populations in Africa. This project is being implemented in partnership with The James Hutton Institute, University of Birmingham, Kenya Agriculture & Livestock Research Organization (KALRO) and the University of Nairobi.</p> <p>For further information on FAIRFARM,</p> <p>Contact the Chief Executive Officer 141 Cornwell Road, Witwatersrand Park, 2014, Braamfontein, Johannesburg, 2001, South Africa.</p> <p>Tel: +27 11 804 3164, +27 11 804 3186</p>
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APPENDIX III: NUTRITION INFORMATION FLIERS FOR DIFFERENT GROUPS, BEAN RECIPES AND COMIC BOOK

Digestion Tips for Consuming Dry Beans
Why do beans cause abdominal discomfort and flatulence?

Beans contain a particular type of carbohydrate, called oligosaccharides. The human body is not able to completely break down oligosaccharides with our digestive enzymes. Instead, the healthy bacteria that live in the large intestine break down these oligosaccharides through fermentation – leading to a sometimes unpleasant result.

Tips to reduce discomfort:
 Take it slow: Eat small amounts and gradually increase your intake.
 Experiment: Try different varieties of beans, not all are made equal.
 Fibre boost: Increase your intake of other fibre-rich foods.
 Rinse: Always thoroughly rinse canned beans before consuming.
 Soak: Soak dry beans for 12-14 hours before cooking to reduce gas.

Unit of measure
 Cup 240-300 ml
 Tablespoon 15 ml
 Teaspoon 5 ml

Utensils needed
 Pots
 Cooking sticks
 Dish/bowl/basin/bucket
 Spoons
 Cups
 Pounding Mortar and Pestle Sieves
 Jars
 Charcoal/ Gau/ Firewood
 Plates
 Knife/Bucket
 Baking tins

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APPENDIX V: SOME RECIPES DEVELOPED

 Bean Recipes

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 Bean Recipes

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Bean Recipes

Bean Queen cakes

Bean Queen Cakes

Bean Cookies

Bean Recipes

Bean pies

Bean doughnuts

Bean cutlets

2022/09/06

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Bean Recipes

Chapati

Mandazi

Kebab

Bean Samosas

2022/09/05

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Bean Recipes

2022/09/05

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APPENDIX VI: COMMERCIALIZATION AND AWARENESS ACTIVITIES

Ziron Pulse documentary, Radio and TV

- [Ziron Pulse Documentary](#)
- [Radio Maisha](#)
- [iNOOrO](#)
- [EBRU TV](#)
- [NTV NEWS](#)
- [KTN NEWS](#)
- [KTN FARMERS](#)

The image displays three screenshots of media content related to the Ziron Pulse project. The top screenshot shows a woman speaking in a field, with a video player interface. The middle screenshot shows a news anchor on a television screen, with a video player interface. The bottom screenshot shows a woman speaking in a field, with a video player interface.

STAR Agatha

HEALTH
Nutritionists introduce recipes for cooking beans rich in iron, zinc

By Agatha Nkomo

• The organisation has come together through a programme to ensure that beans are used to address food security and nutrition, and provide a source of protein for the rural and peri-urban areas.
• The organisation is also working to promote the use of beans in the diet to reduce the prevalence of malnutrition, improve the diversity of diets.

by AGATHA NKOMO
Nutritionist

Star Reporter
24 October 2022 - 23:00

She said they want to promote the adoption and consumption of these beans in Africa, where stunting is a big problem.

Klage said the bean product is a food vehicle that is cheap and widely consumed and they want to ensure it is interesting and appealing to more people.

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Twitter Handles

- https://twitter.com/makauj68/status/1582375965426331650?t=8fCbDepg1r_8X11-Kvyy9Q&s=19
- <https://twitter.com/makauj68/status/1582370334375759872?t=5f1K0QUEF7Hu5cDTXg3ZRQ&s=19>
- https://twitter.com/makauj68/status/1582375965426331650?t=8fCbDepg1r_8X11-Kvyy9Q&s=19

Thread

Dr. Beatrice Klage calls it 'Hidden Hunger' take a keen watch @FANRPAN @MashaScience @otieno_tebby @ZeyniWandati @kalromkulima @Michael_ouma @RobertwaMaina @rodgers_kirwa @uonbi @3davidwanyoike @ResidentVetKe @CheruyotLilian @LynneKolum @PatienceSyombua @ParassisO @MorfoiAjuus

Thread

Caroline Mwenze, an agronomist, speaks on how Kieni is turning to Bean farming due to climate change & nutrition value of beans @kalromkulima @MashaScience @FANRPAN @County19Nyeri @otieno_tebby @lynnecoyugi @AludaGodfrey @JohnatoneMusili @LeeMuriuki9 @LynneKolum @ParassisO

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Commercialization and awareness

Farmer Field day and awareness Gakawa Ward

2023/07/20

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Farmer Field day and awareness Thigu ward

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